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A Review of Current Status of Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria

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Abstract

Agricultural mechanization is the harnessing, controlling and organising all inputs of production such as land, capital, labour, as well as research, education, communication/information, and engineering/technology in agricultural practices (Asoegwu and Asoegwu, 2007). It embraces the use of tools, implements, and machines for agricultural land development, crop production, harvesting, and preparation for storage, storage, and on-farm processing. With enormous advantages obtainable from it and its attendant effect on the wellbeing of the people, Nigeria is lagging behind in fully mechanizing her agricultural sector. This is due to much neglect of the sector by the private sector leaving most investment in the hands of a government. Also, lack of clear cut policies on agricultural mechanization and the inability of successive governments to continue with some good policies of former administrations has reduced mechanizing Nigerian agriculture to mere lip service, therefore affecting the output of this sector. Though the present government is building on the gains of former administration's policies on agriculture, more still need to be done to put the nation on the right path of becoming self-sufficient and exporter of agricultural products (either agro-raw materials or processed products). This paper holistically looks at the current status of agricultural mechanization, its prospects, and challenges. Hence, proffering a way forward to them

Key Words: Agriculture, Challenges, Importance, Mechanization, Policies, and Status.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is a West African country situated on latitude 4°N and longitude 3°14 E in the tropics. She has six (6) geopolitical zones divided into 36 states and 1 federal capital territory, which is the administrative seat of government. It has an estimated population of 184 million people (World Bank, 2017) which is obviously the most populous nation in Africa with over 60% of its citizens below 55 years of age. Her land area is 923,768 km² (92.4 million hectares) out of which about 84 million hectares are arable, and about 40% of this arable land is being cultivated. In addition, Nigeria possesses different distinct climates and four agro-ecological belts (Figure 1) namely: mangrove rainforest, guinea savannah, Sudan savannah and Sahel Savannah for the production of wide range of agricultural products (Othman, 2017).

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Figure 1: Agro-ecological Zones Map of Nigeria.

The agricultural sector is characterized by crop production, the major crops grown in the country are beans, sesame, cashew nuts, cassava, cocoa beans, groundnuts, gum Arabic, kola nut, maize (corn), melon, millet, palm kernels, palm oil, plantains, rice, rubber, sorghum, soybeans, yams, etc.

Agriculture has been the mainstay of the economy since independence and despite several bottlenecks; it remains a resilient sustainer of the populace. Agriculture is an important occupation in Nigeria with over 70% of her population depending on it directly or indirectly for livelihood (Asoegwu and Asoegwu, 2007). Nigeria is endowed with good agronomical and climatic conditions that encourage agricultural practices which contributes 29.15% of Nigeria's total gross domestic product in 2017 (NBS, 2017).

Mechanization simply deals with the act of changing from working largely or exclusively by hand or with animals to the use of machines (Mabayoje, 2017). Agricultural mechanisation is defined as the application of tools, implements, and machines powered by man, animal, and engines as inputs for agricultural production (Clarke and Simalenga, 1997). This includes manufacturing, distribution, use, maintenance (on farm and off-farm) of all types of tools, implements, machinery, and equipment for agricultural production activities (such as land clearing, land levelling, tillage activities, planting and Irrigation, etc.), harvesting, processing activities. The agricultural mechanization devices may be powered by human energy (hand-tool technology) draught animals (animal traction power) and mechanical devices (internal combustion engines) or a combination of any of the three.

1.1. Importance of Agricultural Mechanization

The need for sustainable agricultural mechanisation practices in Nigeria is imperative because the hoe and cutlass agriculture cannot support the food and economic needs of the nation. Some of the need for mechanization is highlighted as follows:

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i. Geometric increase in population

According to the National Population Commission (NPC), 2018, Nigeria has an estimated population strength of over 190 million people. This makes Nigeria the seventh most populous nation in the world and the first in Africa. The high population growth in Nigeria is giving rise to a rapidly increasing demand for food. United Nations predicted a 60% increase in demand for food by 2050 with the surge in the world's population. The present productivity of the agricultural sector in Nigeria is insufficient to meet the food and fiber needs of her current population. This poses a major threat to people's survival and wellbeing. Therefore, there is an expectation for geometric growth in food and fiber production in Nigeria which can only be achieved through sustainable agricultural mechanisation practices.

ii. Diversification of the economy

Nigeria is mono-economy, depending on oil. Hence, the unemployment rate is increasing, productivity is low, and consequently, many Nigerians live in poverty. The contribution of the agricultural sector to the national GDP from 1960 to 2015 showed that it is on a decline (Suberu et al., 2015). A sustained agricultural mechanisation practice would restore the agricultural sector and ultimately the Nigerian economy. Diversification of Nigeria's economy through agricultural mechanization is the only viable way to save the nation from the global fluctuations in oil prices and economic downturn.

iii. Food security in the face of environmental degradation

Traditional farming practices are nature dependent. The replenishment of soil fertility, rainfall, and product drying are exclusively and naturally facilitated, thereby making farm business a risky one. Today, human activities have altered natural phenomena such as drought, desertification and soil erosion. Climate change is a global threat to human existence. The Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) predicts that global warming will reduce agricultural yield by 2% per decade. However, mechanising agricultural productions will go a long way to mitigate the effects of climate change.

iv. Increased farmers' earning

In third world countries and Nigeria in particular, traditional farming activities are characterised with poor earnings. Peasant farmers are naturally the poorest set of people in the society. This unfortunate phenomenon makes all farm activities less attractive to young, energetic and educated youths. Through agricultural mechanisation, just as in the US, farmers' income, the standard of living and prestige would be promoted, thus, making agricultural activities attractive to our educated youths.

v. Agro-Industrial Revolution

Commercial agricultural production through mechanization would make raw materials readily available for agro-allied industries. This can revolutionize local productions, reduce post-harvest losses and create economic opportunities down the value chains.

Therefore, to achieve food security in Sub-Saharan African nations, e.g., Nigeria, Pawlak et al., (2002) opined that there must be significant progress in plant and animal breeding matched with appropriate mechanization that would play a key role in the development of the agricultural sector.

2.0. STATUS OF AGRICULTURAL MECHANIZATION IN NIGERIA.

2.1. What is the Agricultural Mechanization?

Agricultural mechanization is the harnessing, controlling and organising all inputs of production such as land, capital, labour, as well as research, education, communication/information, and engineering/technology in agricultural practices (Asoegwu and Asoegwu, 2007). It embraces the use of tools, implements, and machines

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for agricultural land development, crop production, harvesting, preparation for storage, storage, and on-farm processing. This includes three main power sources: human, animal, and mechanical.

Agricultural mechanization basically deals with the replacement of human and animal labour by mechanical devices in farming activities (Akinbamowo, 2013). In the broadest sense, it embraces the manufacture, distribution, and operation of all types of tools, implements, machines, and equipment for agricultural land development, farm production and crop harvesting, and primary processing (Simalenga, 2000).

Agricultural mechanization often follows various stages, starting from the use of mechanical power for power-intensive operations that require little control (such as milling, threshing, water pumping, or land preparation), followed by control-intensive operations (such as harvesting, weeding, and adapting farming systems and cropping patterns) to increased use of mechanically powered technologies, and finally to automation of production (Akande, 2009). According to Olaoye and Rotimi, (2010), it enhances the cropping intensity and productivity, precision, timelines of operations, efficiency in the utilization of various crop inputs and reduces the losses at different stages of crop production, processing and storage.

2.2. Brief History of Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria

Generally, ancient agriculture was a matter of human sweat and draft animal labour. Using oxen and horses to pull plough was the earliest form of mechanisation. The remaining of farm activities were backbreaking manual operations such as seed planting, weeding, reaping, collecting, bundling, threshing, loading, and transportation of agricultural products.

The invention of internal combustion engines caused a dramatic change that placed tractors at the centre of agricultural mechanisation; this had a profound effect on farm productivity and human society [NAS 2018].

In Nigeria, the earliest tractor unit farm was established in Agege, Lagos state in 1925 while Tractor Hiring Unit (THU) services started in 1956 in the Northern parts (Aboaba, 1977; and Nwosu, 1989). There appears to have been a consensus that THUs provides a viable strategy for promoting mechanization in the developing countries, yet the agriculture of these countries are yet to receive meaningful mechanization (Utaku, 2005). There is now a significant number of THUs all over the different parts of the country.

According to Iheanacho et al., (2003) the machines used for agricultural production in Nigeria include hand tools, the animal is drawn implements, two wheel, and four-wheel drive tractors, motorized or mechanically driven post-harvest handling and processing machines, crop storage equipment and pumps for irrigation.

Nigeria has no single production plant for tractors and machinery; some assembly plants that existed are either moribund or closed down; there are also few indigenous local fabricators that attempt to fabricate simple farm tools, machines and other equipment that are used for various activities on the farm to meet the need of small scale farmers. Most of these machineries cannot compete in the international market due to lack of production capacity and equipment. The country largely depends on imported machineries.

2.3. Current Supply of Agricultural Machines in Nigeria.

The supply of agricultural machines for agricultural production in the country is below the demand. Currently, Nigeria does not have agricultural machinery manufacturers as obtained in developed countries (India, Pakistan, Europe, etc.) but only fabricators. This has limited the capacity of the agricultural machinery production, and technical know-how thus has made the country rely solely on the importation of agricultural machineries.

In Nigeria where 'tractorization' is misconstrued for mechanization, there are only about 30,000 tractors for all 14 million farming groups/families in Nigeria. **Table 1** shows that Nigeria has an average of 7 tractors for every 100 km² of arable land compared to 100, 1,900 and 64,000 tractors for Algeria, Ghana and South Africa

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respectively (Asoegwu and Asoegwu, 2007). Larger percentages of these machines are imported into the Country with no export of locally manufactured agricultural machinery (**Table 2**).

Table 1: Agricultural machinery import and production in Nigeria.

	2013	2014	2015	2016
Total Market Size	63,000	68,000	72,000	104,500
Total Local Production	3,000	3,000	5,000	7,500
Total Imports	60,000	65,000	67,000	97,000

Source: ITA (2016).

Table 2. Inflow and Outflow of agricultural machinery in Nigeria.

	2013	2014	2015 (estimated)	2016 (estimated)
Total Market Size	63,000	68,000	72,000	104,500
Total Local Production	3,000	3,000	5,000	7500
Total Exports	0	0	0	0
Total Imports	60,000	65,000	67,000	97,000
Imports from the U.S.	15,000	18,000	10,000	20,000

Source: www.export.gov.

2.4. Existing Levels of Mechanization in Nigeria.

According (Odigbo and Onwualu, 1994), the following machines are used for agricultural production in Nigeria: hand tools, the animal is drawn implements, two-wheel and four-wheel driven tractors, motorized or mechanically driven post-harvest handling and processing machines, crop storage equipment and pumps for irrigation. Hence, agricultural mechanization practices in Nigeria can be classified into three levels of technology: draught - animal technology (DAT); hand-tool technology (HTT), and engine powered technology (EPT) (Enaboifo and Anerua-Yakubu, 2014). While HTT is applicable to every part of the nation, EPT is more applicable to the Middle Belt and Southern parts of the nation. The application of engine powered technology in Nigeria is when compared to nations like the US, Thailand, China, Brazil, etc.

a) Hand-Tool Technology (HTT)

HTT level of agricultural mechanisation involves the use of tools and implements which are powered by human muscle. HTT is the oldest and the most primitive level of agricultural mechanization (Enaboifo and Anerua-Yakubu, 2014). The hand – tools mostly used in Nigeria include machetes, cutlasses, hoes, diggers, axes, spades, shovels, trowels, rakes, forks, mattocks and shears, knapsack sprayers, jab planters, water can, etc. Agricultural productivity in Nigeria by the use of HTT is highly limited since humans can only develop about 0.08kw of energy depending on environmental conditions and food intake (Kaul and Egbo, 1992).

b) Draught - Animal Technology (DAT)

Animal-drawn technology is predominantly practiced in the Sahel and Sudan savannah ecological zone of Nigeria (North) where soil particles are loosely packed to facilitate animal traction for tillage and transport operations. The use of animals (Bulls, Donkey, etc.) for planting, and operating stationary machines such as water pumps, threshing machines, winnowers, chaff cutters, and grinders is highly limited even if it exists (Musa, 1988).

c) Engine – Powered Technology (EPT)

EPT level of agricultural mechanization is the most advanced, sophisticated and efficient one. It involves a very wide range of implements, machines, and equipment powered by diesel/ gasoline engines and electric motors. These equipment used in Nigeria include bulldozers, 4 wheel tractors, 2 wheel tractors, boom sprayers, ridge plough, disc plough, harrow plough, mechanised grain threshers, mechanised milling machines, mechanised

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garri grater and fryers, mechanised rice harvester, mechanised winnowers, mechanised driers, cassava planting machine, etc. There is no statistical information on the level of EPT use in Nigerian agriculture, but it is observed to be relatively low. The tractorization density of Nigeria is just 0.27 horsepower per hectare which is far below FAO's recommended density of 1.5 horsepower per hectare (the Sahel, 2017).

2.5. State of Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria

In modern times, powered machinery has replaced many jobs formerly carried out by men or animals such as oxen, horses, and mules. The level, appropriate choice and subsequent proper use of farm machinery and equipment in agriculture has a direct and significant effect on achievable levels of land productivity, labour productivity, the profitability of farming, the environment and the quality of life of people engaged in agriculture (CRIT, 2012).

Agricultural mechanization is low in Nigeria with a mechanization rate of 0.27 horsepower per hectare which is well below the FAO's recommended rate of 1.5 horsepower per hectare (the Sahel, 2017). **Table 3** shows that an average of 7 tractors for every 100km² of arable land in Nigeria compared to Algeria, Ghana and South Africa have 100, 1900 and 64000 tractors respectively while **Figure 2** presents the number of tractors in use within the period covered in the Country.

Table 3: Agricultural machinery, tractors per 100 km² of arable land.

Country	2003	2004	2005	2006
Nigeria	6.9	7.00	6.6	6.8
Algeria	97,800	97,809	100,128	102,636
Ghana	1,920	1,912	1,803	-
South Africa	65,475	63,200	-	-

Source: World Bank (2012).

Figure 2: Bar Chart showing the number of tractors in use in Nigeria within the period covered

Source: Omofunmi and Olaniyan, (2018).

Onwualu and Pawa (2004) reported that 90% of Nigeria's agricultural work is done with hand tools, 7% with animal-drawn tools and only 3% with engine powered technology.

In the 2010 rainy season, (**Table 4**) only 6 percent of the country's farmers in the North West region used tractors, either their own or rented North Central had the highest, 15 percent. Animal traction is still mostly used particularly in the North East with over 60 percent usage (Takeshima et al., 2013b). Though animal traction is intermediary compared to tractors with more than 10 horsepower (hp); hence, the level of mechanization remains low (Takeshima and Salau, 2010).

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Table 4: Percentage of Farmers using tractors or animal traction in 2010 rainy session in Nigeria.

Region	Share (%) of farm households using tractors or animal traction						No tractor/ animal traction
	Tractor			Animal traction			
	Total	Owned Tractor	Rented Tractor only	Total	Owned animal	Rented animal only	
NW	6	2	4	27	17	10	67
NE	2	1	1	62	36	26	36
NC	15	4	11	5	3	2	80
SE	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
SS	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
SW	4	3	1	1	1	0	95

Source: Takeshima et al. (2013b)

Research showed that though mechanization is low, rice has significant tractorization which account for a small share of cultivated area (less than 10 percent) in Nigeria (Table 5).

Table 5: Tractorized areas in Nigeria by crop (10,000 hectares, the year 2010 & 2013)

Methods	Rice	Maize	Sorghum	Millet	Cowpea	G nuts	Cassava	Yam	Vega	Total
LSMS	86	24	15	5	8	6	13	7	1	185
FAO	118	35	25	8	11	12	34	16	1	258

Sources: LSMS (2010) and FAO (2013).

In 2012, Dr. Akinwumi Adesina opined that 746,666 tractors are needed to mechanized Nigerian agriculture (Yusuf, 2014). Since ‘tractorization’ is often misconstrued for mechanization in Nigeria, it can then be adjudged that Nigerian agriculture is still dominated by the hoe-cutlass technology (Itodo, 2016). This accounts for the retarded growth in the sector and threat of hunger, disease, and poverty in the Country.

2.6. Policies and Organization for Promoting Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria

After the discovery of oil at Oloibiri, Bayelsa State in 1959, Nigeria agricultural productivity continues to lag behind as a source of foreign exchange earnings. Since agriculture is generally seen to propel economic growth and facilitate the achievement of structural transformation and diversification of economies globally, successive administrations from 1960 to date have put in place several food policies aimed at making the sector take its rightful place.

2.6.1. Policies for Promoting Agricultural Mechanization

According to Nehemiah (2015), the period 1960-1972 was characterized by very limited policies in favour of agricultural development; but Nigeria began to witness agricultural development policies from 1973 that supported mechanization of the sector as highlighted below:

- National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP), 1973:** The target of the programme accelerated the production of major staple crops. It significantly promoted the production of maize, cassava, rice, and wheat in the Northern states through subsistent production within a short period of time.

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- b) **Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank (NACB), 1973:** It was mandated to provide loans to farmers to encourage commercial/mechanized farming. The target was achieved through loan grants to farmers at a single digit interest rate.
- c) **Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs), 1975:** Its establishment promoted the introduction of modern technology through agricultural research and extension services.
- d) **National Grains Reserve Programme (NGRP), 1975:** It promoted modern infrastructural facilities development in the nation for storage of grains. This programme established modern grain silos in all state capitals of grain producing states.
- e) **Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), 1976:** It was introduced to mobilize people to take an active part in agricultural production. Under the programme, agricultural inputs such as improved seeds, fertilizers, credit, and agricultural mechanization activities were highly subsidized in the nation.
- f) **The River Basin Development Authorities, 1977:** The mandate of the authorities were to boost economic potentials of the existing water bodies particularly irrigation and fishery with hydroelectric power generation and domestic water supply as secondary objectives (Ayoola, 2001). Eleven River Basin Development Authorities Centers were built across the nation and equipped with farm machineries.
- g) **The Green Revolution, 1980:** The programme was mandated to provide improved seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, irrigation, water, credit, appropriate mechanization, agro service centers, improved marketing system, and pricing policy as well as other incentives necessary for agricultural development. The target was to make the country self-sufficient in basic food production within five years and to rehabilitate and restore exportation of agro product in seven years.
- h) **National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA), 1992:** The mandate of NALDA was to develop lands for massive mechanized farms. The authorities were heavily equipped with modern land clearing equipment such as Bulldozers, etc. The opening of virgin lands for agricultural production was achieved.
- i) **Establishment of Agricultural Institutions:** Institution for supporting agricultural mechanization were established across the nation, e.g., National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, Ilorin (NCAM) established in 1990, Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Service (AERLS) at the ABU, Zaria established in 1963; International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) established in 1967, International Livestock Centre for Africa (ILCA), etc.
- j) **National Fadama Development Project (NFDP), 1993:** It was designed to empower communities and strengthen agricultural development in irrigable lands in all states of the country through agro-financing support (World Bank, 2015). Production of food products during dry season boosted farmers' economy and food supply.
- k) **National, Special Programme on Food Security (NSPFS), 2002:** Its objectives were to assist farmers in achieving their potential for increasing output and incomes on a sustainable basis; strengthen the effectiveness of research and extension services in bringing technology and new farming practices developed by research institutes to farmers and ensuring greater relevance of research to the farmers; concentrate initial efforts in pilot areas for maximum effect and ease of replication by non-project farmers; train and educate farmers in the effective utilization of available land, water and other resources and facilities to produce food and create employment on a sustainable basis; and utilize international experience for integrated farming practices in Nigeria to maximize use of existing facilities and knowledge to spread benefits to wider areas.
- l) **Root and Tuber Expansion Programme (RTEP) 2003:** The goal of RTEP was to improve the living conditions, income and food security of smallholder households in the programme areas. The specific objectives were to raise the level of productivity of the target groups further,

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enhance/improve the processing technologies/techniques and promote the marketing of these commodities, particularly cassava produce and its products.

- m) **The Seven-Point Agenda: Agricultural Policy Thrust, 2007:** The policy centered on increasing agricultural production through increased budgetary allocation and promotion of the necessary developmental, supportive and service-oriented activities to enhance production and productivity and marketing opportunities, increasing fiscal incentives to agriculture, among other sector, and reviewing import waiver anomalies with appropriate fiscal policies on agricultural imports; promotion of agricultural machinery and inputs through favorable tariff policy (FMARD, 2007).
- n) **Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), 2012:** Its target was to:
- i. Eliminate corruption in the seed and fertiliser sector,
 - ii. Improve the functioning of market institutions,
 - iii. Establish staple crop processing zones to attract private sector and reduce post-harvest losses,
 - iv. Add value to locally produced , and
 - v. Foster rural economic growth.
 - vi. Assure food security,
 - vii. Assure reduce the expenditure of foreign exchange on food imports,
 - viii. Assure diversify the economy,
 - ix. Assure generate foreign exchange, and
 - x. Assure create jobs.
- o) **Agricultural Equipment Hiring Enterprises (AEHE), 2014:** AEHE Targets to achieve the following in collaboration with Public Private Partnership (PPP):
- i. Make available a minimum of 6000 units of tractors;
 - ii. Make available a minimum of 6000 power tiller;
 - iii. Make available 13000 units of harvest and post-harvest machines to mechanize agriculture.
 - iv. To lease/ hire out various kinds of agricultural equipment for land preparation,
 - v. Harvest and post-harvest activities.
 - vi. Establish 1200 AEHE centers across the nation.
- p) **The Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP), 2016:** It aims to build on the successes of the ATA and closing key gaps noticed in it. The new policy regime is founded on the following guiding principles, a number of which are carryovers from the ATA reflecting the strong desire for policy stability. New elements added to reflect the lessons from the ATA, as well as priorities emerging from the aspirations of the Buhari Administration:
1. **Agriculture as a business** – focusing the policy instruments on a government-enabled, private sector-led engagement as the main growth driver of the sector.
 2. **Agriculture as key to long-term economic growth and security**—focusing policy instruments on ensuring that the commercialization of agriculture includes technologies, financial services, inputs supply chains, and market linkages that directly engage poor rural farmers because rural economic growth will play a critical role in the country’s successful job creation, economic diversity, improved security, and sustainable economic growth.
 3. **Food as a human right** – focusing the policy instruments for agricultural development on the social responsibility of government with respect to food security, social security and equity in the Nigerian society; and compelling the government to recognize, protect and fulfill the irreducible minimum degree of freedom of the people from hunger and malnutrition.
 4. **Value chain approach** – focusing the policy instruments for enterprise development across successive stages of the commodity value chains for the development of crop, livestock and

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fisheries sub-sectors, namely input supply, production, storage, processing/utilization, marketing, and consumption.

5. **Prioritizing crops** – focusing policy on achieving improved domestic food security and boosting export earnings requires a measure of prioritization. Therefore, for domestic crops, the initial focus in 2016 – 2018 will be expanding the production of rice, wheat, maize, soya beans, and tomatoes. For export crops, the initial focus will be on cocoa, cassava, oil palm, sesame, and gum Arabic. In 2018 onwards, the export focus will add on bananas, avocado, mango, fish and cashew nuts.
6. **Market orientation** – focusing policy instruments on stimulating agricultural production on a sustainable basis, and stimulating supply and demand for agricultural produce by facilitating linkages between producers and off takers, while stabilizing prices or reducing price volatility for agricultural produce through market-led price stabilization mechanisms (commodity exchanges, negotiated off-take agreements, extended farm-gate price under value chains coordination mechanisms, agricultural insurance, etc.)
7. **Factoring Climate change and Environmental sustainability** – focusing policy instruments on the sustainability of the use of natural resources (land and soil, water and ecosystems) with the future generation in mind while increasing agricultural production, marketing, and other human activities in the agricultural sector.
8. **Participation and inclusiveness** – focusing instruments on measures to maximize the full participation of stakeholders including farmer’s associations, cooperatives, and other groups, as well as NGOs, CBOs, CSOs, development partners and the private sector.
9. **Policy integrity** – focusing policy instruments on measures for sanitizing the business environment for agriculture, in terms of accountability, transparency and due process of law, ensuring efficient allocation and use of public funding and fighting corruption on all programmes involving public resources.
10. **Nutrition sensitive agriculture** – focusing policy instruments on addressing the issues of stunting, wasting, underweight and other manifestations of hunger and malnutrition with particular reference to the vulnerable groups, which include children under 5, nursing mothers and persons with chronic illness and disabilities
11. **Agriculture’s Linkages with Other Sectors** – focusing policy instruments on the connected relationship between agriculture and other sectors at federal and state levels, particularly industry, environment, power, energy, works and water sectors (FMARD, 2016).

2.6.2. Organization for Promoting Agricultural Mechanization

In a way to boost and encourage agricultural mechanization, government over the years established various organizations to promote better ways of doing agriculture through research and development. **Table 6** presents the activities of various Agric-based research institutes in Nigeria.

Table 6: Activities of Agric-Based Research Institutes in Nigeria.

S/No.	Research Institute	Mandate	Ecological Zone Covered
1.	National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Idofian, Ilorin, Kwara State. E-mail:ncamcontact@yahoo.com	Research into agricultural mechanization through the development of sustainable indigenous mechanization technologies.	All ecological zones in Nigeria.
2.	Cocoa Research institute of Nigeria (CRIN), Ibadan. E-mail:	Research into the genetic improvement and production of cocoa, cashew, kola, tea, and coffee.	Ecological zones covered by the specified crops.

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3.	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Ibadan. E-mail: info@frin.gov.ng ; edfrin@frin.gov.ng	Research into forestry, agroforestry, wildlife, and environmental production and conservation. Total farming systems for the ecological zones encompassing Kano, Sokoto, Katsina, Kaduna and Kebbi and the Zamfara States.	Ecological zones encompassing Kano, Sokoto, Katsina, Kaduna, Kebbi and Zamfara states.
4.	Institute for Agricultural Research (IAR), Zaria. E-mail: iar@abu.edu.ng / iar.abu.edu.ng	Research into the genetic improvement of sorghum, groundnut, cowpea, cotton, sunflower, maize. Total farming systems for the ecological zones covered by Kano, Sokoto, Katsina, Kaduna Kebbi and the Zamfara States.	Northern and Western zones of Nigeria.
5	Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T), Ibadan. E-mail: diart@infoweb.abs.net	Research into kenaf, jute, and soil and water management. Total farming systems for the ecological zones encompassing Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, Ekiti, Edo and Delta States.	Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, Ekiti, Edo and Delta States.
6.	Lake Chad Research Institute (LCRI), Maiduguri. E-mail:	Research into the genetic improvement of millet, wheat, and barley. Total farming systems for the ecological zones covered by Borno, Jigawa, Yobe, Gombe, Bauchi, and the Adamawa States.	Ecologies are encompassing Borno, Yobe, Gombe, Jigawa, Bauchi and Adamawa states.
7.	National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services (NAERLS), Zaria. E-mail: director@naerls.gov.ng	Co-ordination of all agricultural extension and specialized support activities in crops, livestock, fisheries, forestry, irrigation, and food technology	All ecological zones of Nigeria.
8.	National Animal Production Research Institute (NAPRI), Zaria. E-mail:	Research into animal production and animal products.	Ecological zones covered by the specified animals.
9.	National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI), Badeggi. E-mail:	Research into the genetic improvement and total farming systems of rice, soybean, benniseed, and sugarcane; and extension services in the middle belt.	The middle belt zones.
10.	National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research (NIFFR), New Bussa. E-mail: niffish@yahoo.com , niffish@gmail.com	Research into the genetic improvement of freshwater fish species, other aquatic resources and their production in Nigeria; and Research into long term effects of man-made lakes on ecology and environment.	Ecological zones covered by the fisheries and aquatic resources.
11.	National Institute for Horticultural Research (NIHORT), Ibadan. E-mail:	Research into genetic improvement and production of fruits and vegetables as well as ornamental plants.	Ecological zones covered by the specified plants.
12.	National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI), Umudike. E-mail:	Research into the genetic improvement of cassava, yam, coco-yam, irish potato, and ginger. Total farming systems, research and extension services in South-East zones.	Anambra, Enugu, Cross River, Ebonyi, Imo, Abia, Rivers State, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa and Plateau States.

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13.	National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI), Vom, Jos. E-mail:	Research into all aspects of livestock and animal diseases; their treatment and control. Development and production of animal vaccines and sera, etc.	Ecological zones covered by the animals.
14.	Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research (NIOMR), Lagos. E-mail:	Research into the resource and physical characteristics of Nigerian territorial waters and the high sea beyond; and Research into genetic improvement of marine and brackish water fish species oceanography and aquatic resources, their production and processing.	Ecological zones covered by the ocean and territorial waters.
15.	Nigerian Institute for Oil Palm Research (NIFOR), Benin City. E-mail: info@nifor.org.ng	Research into the genetic improvement, production, and processing of oil palm, raphia, date, coconut, and ornamental palms.	Ecological zones covered by the specified plants.
16.	Rubber Research Institute of Nigeria (RRIN), Benin City. E-mail:	Research into the genetic improvement, production, and processing of natural rubber and other latex producing plants, such as gum arabic.	Ecological zones covered by the specified plants.
17.	Federal Institute for Industrial Research (FIRO), Lagos. E-mail:	Research into agro-industrial and food processing technology and upgrading of indigenous production and processes; and Food science and technology, design and fabrication of machines.	Ecological zones covered by the plants.
18.	Nigerian Institute for Trypanosomiasis Research (NITR), Kaduna. E-mail:	Research into tsetse and Simulium flies and diagnostic methods on the control of trypanosomiasis and onchocerciasis.	Ecological zones covered by the animal.
19.	Nigerian Stored Product Research Institute (NSPRI), Ilorin. E-mail:	Research into the improvement of storage and preservation systems on major food and industrial crops; and Studies on stored product pests, pesticides formulation, and residue analysis.	Ecological zones covered by the plants.
20.	National Research Institute for Chemical Technology (NARICT), Zaria. E-mail: contactus@narict.gov.ng	Research into hides, skins, leather, industrial chemicals, polymers, and plastics.	Ecological zones covered by the specified plants and animal.
21.	National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD), Abuja. E-mail:	Research into medicinal plants/herbs and drugs development and formulary.	Ecological zones covered by the specified plants.
22.	National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NAGRAB), Ibadan. E-mail: info@nacgrab.gov	Husbanding of plant and animal genetic resource. Development resources in genetics.	Ecological zones covered by the specified plants and animal.

Source: Oni (2004).

3.0. CONTRIBUTIONS OF NCAM TO AGRICULTURAL MECHANISATION DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

3.1. Machinery Development

As part of the Centre's mandate to develop a low cost machine, the Centre has developed several machines for the various types of crop grown in Nigeria. **Table 7** presents the various types of machines developed by the Centre. It is clear from this table that NCAM paid more attention to root and tuber crops most especially

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cassava. This came as a result of government's involvement in promoting cassava for export of cassava chips to China and for the incorporation of 10% cassava flour with 90% wheat flour for the making of bread in Nigeria. **Figure 3** presents the array of some agricultural machinery and equipment developed by NCAM.

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Source: Kasali, (2018).

Table 7. List of some Agricultural Machineries and Equipment developed by NCAM

Type of Crop					Other use
Cereals	Legumes	Roots & Tubers	Fruits and Vegetables	Tree	
i. Hand held maize cone sheller	i. Tractor mounted groundnut digger/shaker	i. semi-automated cassava stem planter	i. Melon sheller (manual and motorized)	i. Motorized palm fruit stripper	i. 64 tray cabinet dryer (kerosene fired)
ii. Bench mounted maize sheller	ii. Groundnut decorticator	ii. Cassava lifter (Manually operated)	ii. Okra slicer (Manually operated)	ii. Motorized palm fruit sterilizer	ii. Batch dryer (kerosene fired)
iii. Marubi maize sheller	iii. Cowpea thresher	iii. Tractor drawn cassava harvester	iii. Motorized mango juice extractor	iii. Palm fruit digester (Manually operated and motorized)	iii. Fish smoking kiln (Charcoal fired)
iv. Seed planter	iv. Seed dehuller	iv. Improved cassava peeling tool (Manually operated)	iv. Plantain slicer	iv. Motorized palm oil clarifier	iv. Motorized multi-purpose milling machine
v. Jab planter		v. Cassava peeler (Motorized)	v. Shelled melon seed separator	v. Fibre separator	v. Motorized oil expeller
vi. Multi-crop thresher		vi. Cassava washer (Motorized)		vi. Hydraulic press	vi. Trike-tor 300 (Farm bike)
vii. Rice destoner		vii. Cassava grater (threadled and motorized)		vii. Palm kernel cracker	vii. Seed treatment drum
viii. Farm level paddy parboiler		viii. Motorized cassava chipper (for producing i) Threadlike shaped cassava chips and ii) cubic shaped cassava chips)		viii. Motorized coffee depulper	viii. Manual seed and fertilizer broadcaster
ix. Hand-held rice harvester		ix. Cassava grater cum chipper (Motorized)		ix. Motorized coffee dehuller cum polisher	ix. Improved long hand is weeding hoe
x. Rice transplanter (under testing)		x. Cassava dewatering press (single and double pole types)		x. Motorized cocoa oil expeller	x. Rotary hand push is weeding hoe
xi. Rice Thresher		xi. Spring-loaded cassava dewatering press			xi. Mixing machine
		xii. Motorized cassava mash shifter (vertical and horizontal types)			xii. Long handle hoe
		xiii. Cassava sedimentation tank			
		xiv. Gari communal fryer			
		xv. Gari industrial fryer			
		xvi. Motorized hammer mill with and without cyclone			
		xvii. Motorized yam dicer			

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Figure 3: Some NCAM Developed Agricultural Machines.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(a, b & c): NCAM Trike-tor 300 and associated implements

(d): NCAM Four-Wheel Tractor

(e) NCAM Two Row Cassava Stem Planter

(f) NCAM Four Row Seed Planter

(g) NCAM Mechanical Garri Fryer

(h) NCAM Cassava Tuber Peeling Machine (i) NCAM Multi-Crop Thresher

(j) Melon Seed Shelling Machine

(k) Mini-Rice Thresher

(l) Motorized Maize Sheller

(m) Hammer Mill with Cyclone

3.2. Machinery Testing and Certification.

It is part of the Centre's mandate to test any agricultural machinery and equipment imported into the country for use in Nigerian agriculture, NCAM has evaluated 79 tractors of different makes and models since 2001 to date. Table 8 presents the list of tractors evaluated by the Centre. Most of these tractors evaluated by the Centre were tractors imported mainly from India and China.

Table 8. List of Tractors Evaluated by NCAM: 2001 – To Date

S/No.	Name of Tractor	Type of Tractor	Engine Rated Power (Hp)	Country of Origin	Year Evaluated
1.	VITEC	Four-Wheel	16	China	2001
2.	Eicher 485DI	Four-Wheel	42	India	2002
3.	Mahindra 585DI	Four-Wheel	50	India	2002
4.	Eicher (Euro Power) 6100	Four-Wheel	60	India	2003
5.	Changzhou Walking Tractor	Two-Wheel	13.2	China	2004
6.	Mahindra B-275 DI	Four-Wheel	39	India	2005
7.	Mahindra 575 DI	Four-Wheel	45	India	2005
8.	Mahindra 605 DI	Four-Wheel	60	India	2005
9.	SWARAJ 855	Four-Wheel	55	India	2005
10.	SWARAJ 978FE	Four-Wheel-Drive	78	India	2005
11.	HRT-195 Walking Tractor	Two-Wheel	12	China	2005
12.	Mahindra 585 DI	Four-Wheel	50	India	2005
13.	UMZ 6AKM 40.2	Four-Wheel	65	Ukraine	2005 - 2006
14.	Foton 450	Four-Wheel	45	China	2006

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15.	Foton 650	Four-Wheel	65	China	2006
16.	Foton 824	Four-Wheel-Drive	80	China	2006
17.	Top Tech	Four-Wheel-Drive	69	China	2006
18.	SONALIKA DI-75	Four-Wheel	70	India	2006
19.	URSUS 5312	Four-Wheel	70	Poland	2006
20.	Merry tiller	Two-Wheel	5	United States of America	2006
21.	FARMTRAC 60	Four-Wheel	50	India	2007
22.	FARMTRAC 70	Four-Wheel	60	India	2007
23.	FARMTRAC 80	Four-Wheel	73	India	2007
24.	POWERTRAC 455	Four-Wheel	55	India	2007
25.	TAFE 7502	Four-Wheel	75	India	2007
26.	Balwan 500	Four-Wheel	50	India	2007
27.	CLAAS CELTIS 426 RA	Four-Wheel-Drive	74.4	Germany	2007
28.	LEAD SOLUTION U60	Four-Wheel-Drive	57	Korea	2008
29.	YTO X-704	Four-Wheel-Drive	69	China	2008
30.	Foton Europard 704	Four-Wheel-Drive	69	China	2008
31.	Foton Europard 600	Four-Wheel	59	China	2008
32.	DONGFENG 700	Four-Wheel	69	China	2008
33.	BELARUS 82.1	Four-Wheel-Drive	82.1	BELARUS	2008
34.	KAMA 550	Four-Wheel	54.3	China	2008
35.	WEITUO SWT-854	Four-wheel-Drive	83.8	China	2008
36.	BELARUS 800	Four-Wheel	80	BELARUS	2008
37.	RICH combine harvester	Two- Wheel	6.9	China	2008
38.	Mahindra B-275	Four-Wheel	39	India	2008
39.	Mahindra 605 DI	Four-Wheel	60	India	2008
40.	Mahindra 705 DI	Four Wheel	70	India	2008
41.	Mahindra 8000 2WD	Four-Wheel	80	India	2008
42.	TAK 750 DI	Four-Wheel	50	India	2009
43.	TAK 75 DI	Four-Wheel	75	India	2009
44.	TAK 90 DI	Four-Wheel-Drive	90	India	2009
45.	ZETOR (PROXIMA 75)	Four-Wheel-Drive	72	Czech Republic	2009
46.	AGROLUX 75e	Four-Wheel	70	India	2009
47.	FARMTRAC 80E	Four -Wheel	80	India	2009
48.	SONALIKA DI75	Four-Wheel-Drive	75	India	2010
49.	YTO-X750	Four-Wheel	74	China	2010
50.	YTO-X754	Four-Wheel-Drive	74	China	2010
51.	BASAK 2073 SH	Four-Wheel	75	Turkey	2010
52.	Landini 7860	Four-Wheel-Drive	73.5	Italy	2010
53.	Landini Global farm 100	Four-Wheel-Drive	97.3	Italy	2010
54.	VARI Multipurpose Mini- Tractor	Two-Wheel	5.1	Czech Republic	2011
55.	Millat MF 375	Four-Wheel	72	Pakistan	2011
56.	Farm Bike (Trike-tor)	Three-Wheel	20	Nigeria	2011
57.	Bull 55 Series Utility	Four-Wheel	55	Czech Republic	2011
58.	Rumptstad Single Axle Tractor	Two-Wheel	12	Netherlands	2012
59.	Luzhong 700 Tractor	Four-Wheel	59	China	2013
60.	Foton Europard 820	Four-Wheel	82	China	2013
61.	Hi Power Single Axle Tractor	Two-Wheel	13	Japan	2013
62.	Foton Europard 824	Four-Wheel-Drive	82	China	2014
63.	Shuhe SH 750	Four-Wheel	73.8	China	2015
64.	Belarus 510	Four-Wheel	57	Belarus	2015
65.	Belarus 522	Four-Wheel-Drive	62	Belarus	2015
66.	Belarus 820	Four-Wheel-Drive	81	Belarus	2015
67.	ZoomLion RM754-A	Four-Wheel-Drive	73.8	China	2015
68.	New Holland TT75	Four-Wheel	75	India	2015
69.	RD 110 DI-2T	Two-Wheel	11	Indonesia	2016
70.	RD 85 DI-2S	Two-Wheel	8.5	Indonesia	2016
71.	DANMAR Mini Tractor and its associated implements	Two-Wheel	6.5	Slovakia	2016
72.	JS-800	Four-Wheel	79.1	China	2016
73.	JS-1204A	Four-Wheel-Drive	118.2	China	2016
74.	TS 604	Four-Wheel-Drive	59.1	China	2016
75.	SAME Explorer 85 Special	Four-Wheel-Drive	80.2	Italy	2016
76.	TS 804III	Four-Wheel-Drive	79.1	China	2016

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77.	Dakr Mini Tractor and its associated implements	Two-Wheel	5.5	Czech Republic	2016
78.	PREET 9049	Four-Wheel-Drive	90	India	2017
79.	Mahindra 6005 2WD	Four-Wheel	60	India	2017

Source: Kasali, (2018).

3.3. Standards and Test Codes

The Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) is committed to providing standards and quality assurance services for all products, services, and processes in Nigeria in line with international best practices and to ensure continual improvement. The Centre, in collaboration with SON, has developed seven Standards and Test Codes for agricultural equipment namely:

- i. Nigerian Standard Test Code for Grain and Seed Cleaners.
- ii. Nigerian Standard Test Code for Maize Sheller.
- iii. Nigerian Standard Test Code for Agricultural Tillage Discs.
- iv. Nigerian Standard Specification for Agricultural Tillage Disc: Part I – Concave Discs.
- v. Nigerian Standard Specification for Agricultural Tillage Disc: Part II – Flat Discs.
- vi. Nigerian Standard Terminology for Tillage and Tillage Equipment.
- vii. Nigerian Standard Test Code for Groundnut Sheller.

The Centre had equally, in collaboration with the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) prepared four Standards and Test Codes awaiting approval of the Nigerian Standards Council within the years under review. The drafts are:

- i. Draft Nigerian Standards Test Code for Grain planters.
- ii. Draft Nigerian Standards Test Code for Grain harvesters.
- iii. Draft Nigerian Standards Test Code for Weights and Measures.
- iv. Draft Nigerian Standards Test Codes for Grain Threshers.

3.4. Training organized by the Centre

NCAM saddled with the responsibility of mechanizing Nigerian agriculture have conducted series of training over the years in impacting current trend practice of farming and agro-processing operations to farmers, tractor operators and agro-processors in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria and across West African region.

3.5. Extension Services

The Centre over the years has been involved in the fabrication and installation of NCAM equipment to some of the States in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. Today, these agricultural machinery and equipment are being seen by our own farmers as one of the most reliable machine products farmers in the country could rely and depend on for their farming and agro-processing operations. Some of the Nigerian and foreign agencies that enjoyed NCAM's patronage are the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO); Agricultural Development Programme (ADP); LADMOK Company, Abeokuta; Sierra Leone government, Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD), Food for All International (FFAI), South Korean government, JICA, etc.

4.0. CHALLENGES OF AGRICULTURAL MECHANIZATION IN NIGERIA

According to Kasali (2018) and Sahel (2017), some of the clog in the wheel of mechanizing Nigerian agricultural sector includes:

4.1. Funding of Research Activities

Research activities which are a major source contributing to increased productivity in the agricultural sector have not been adequately funded by the government. Most research findings originating from government established Universities and Research Institutions in Nigeria have not been properly coordinated and disseminated to farmers who are meant to be the ultimate beneficiaries of these findings.

4.2. Poor Ratio between Extension Agent and Farmer

As essential as their services are, no serious attention is paid to the extension services by both federal and state governments. The retired ones are not replaced, and the few available are not motivated. This has hindered many research successes getting to the end users who really need them. The present average ratio of 1:3011 was reported by (NAERLS Field survey, 2012) as shown in **Table 9**.

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Table 9. Nigeria's Extension Agent: Farm Families ratio, 2008 – 2012.

State	EA: farm families ratio trend				
	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Borno	1:1971	1:1971	NA	1:1964	1:1964
Yobe	1:1800	1:1800	1:1000	1:2472	1:2472
Bauchi	1:1300	1:1300	1:1700	NA	1:1731
Gombe	1:1350	1:1741	1:1225	1:1225	1:1225
Adamawa	1:2549	1:2459	1:1000	1:1212	1:1212
Jigawa	1:1500	1:1500	1:1389	1:2054	NA
Katsina	NA	NA	NA	1:3000	1:3000
Sokoto	NA	1:4013	1:4050	1:4050	1:4000
Kebbi	1:1600	1:3749	1:3749	1:2608	NA
Zamfara	1:1490	1:1400	1:1479	1:1944	1:1944
Kano	NA	NA	NA	1:844	NA
Kaduna	1:3000	1:3000	NA	1:3240	1:3240
Taraba	1:3200	1:3200	1:3200	1:3200	1:3200
Plateau	1:1000	1:1800	1:3038	1:3187	NA
Nasarawa	1:2313	1:3200	1:1317	1:1156	1:1368
FCT	1:1148	1:1700	1:1282	NA	NA
Niger	1:2280	1:2160	1:3000	1:2000	1:2000
Kwara	1:4025	1:3843	1:4000	1:2500	1:2190
Kogi	1:1526	1:1526	1:2160	1:1000	1:1000
Benue	1:2630	1:3640	1:1747	1:3500	1:4000
Osun	1:3217	1:3097	NA	1:1984	1:1984
Oyo	1:500	1:500	1:3773	1:800	1:800
Ekiti	1:42	1:42	1:2750	1:3000	1:3000
Ogun	1:3711	1:3711	1:2812	1:3364	1:3364
Lagos	1:1100	1:1350	1:1612	1:1612	1:1612
Edo	1:2100	1:2100	1:3750	1:3750	1:3750
Delta	1:800	1:800	1:1559	1:1559	1:1559
Ondo	1:1500	1:1500	1:1480	1:1480	NA
Anambra	1:6048	1:3799	1:9409	1:9409	1:9409
Enugu	1:746	1:850	1:6013	1:6848	1:3081
Ebonyi	1:6046	1:1960	NA	NA	NA
Cross river	NA	NA	1:4458	1:4013	1:4721
Rivers	NA	NA	1:6748	1:6749	1:3450
Abia	1:2632	1:2952	1:2700	1:2700	1:2700
Akwa Ibom	NA	NA	1:3086	1:3086	1:2902
Imo	1:3333	1:3333	NA	1:1300	1:1000
Bayelsa	NA	NA	NA	1:10,568	1:10,568
Year average EA:FFs ratio	1:1700	1:2132	1:3385	1:2950	1: 3011

Source: NAERLS Field survey (2012)

4.3. Weak Synergy existing between Financial Institutions and Research Institutions

In developed countries there exist a strong synergy between financial institutions and research institutes into agricultural related activities. The situation in Nigeria is different because most financial institutions believe in businesses that could bring quick financial returns on investment than a research work that might take years to achieve its aims and objectives. In most time, the financial institution does not welcome such innovative research work that can bring social benefits to farmers and the society.

4.4. Low Private Investment

Moreover, the agricultural research activities in Nigeria have seen low interest from the private investors. This has tactically left these research activities in hand of government unlike in the developed world where it is driven by the private sector. This was due to the neglect of agriculture by the Government and her

ability to see agriculture as a business. The role of government should be policy formulation and creation of a conducive environment for private sector participation.

4.5. Lack of Synergy between Stakeholders

This also has greatly slowed down the development of agricultural machinery research in Nigeria. Academic and research institutions, financial institutions, farmers, investors and other stakeholders in the sector have weak linkages and working relationship. This has resulted in the poor dissemination of breakthroughs in research to the farmers; lack of adequate information to access loan facilities, etc. This should be tackled through various appraisal seminars, conferences between relevant stakeholders and exhibitions/farmers field days in the sector.

4.6. Fragmented Farming

Most farmers in Nigeria are small-holders farmers who are managing few hectares of land for the farming operation. As a result, the average farm size of a smallholder farmer in Nigeria ranges from 0.7-2.2 hectares. Fragmented land holdings often make it difficult to use mechanization and cause inefficiencies in agricultural production. The output in their farm is low resulting from low return on investment. Most of these farmers are used to the traditional way of farming which involves the use of hoes and cutlasses. This has really made it difficult for farmers in the country to adopt the use of agricultural machinery in boosting their farm produce which is expected to lead to a high return on investment.

4.7. Local Knowledge

A lack of access to information regarding mechanization limits stakeholders across the agricultural sector from adopting mechanization. To compound this, the extension delivery system is inefficient; as a result, extension agents with information on mechanization opportunities are typically unable to transfer this information.

4.8. High Cost of Machines

The cost of mechanization input for crop production and processing is very high due to the surge in foreign exchange. Moreover, it is difficult for farmers and processors to sustain the recurring costs of operating equipment. Poor access to finance is a major constraint to the adoption of mechanization as it makes it difficult for scaling service providers and new entries to access the capital required to procure equipment.

4.9. Poor Access to Maintenance Services and Spare Parts

A lack of local expertise for the repair and maintenance of machineries is a major constraint to the sustainable use of mechanization in Nigeria. Currently, there are not enough technicians trained to deal with the types and brands of machines available. The poor quality of maintenance services for agricultural machinery is fueled by a lack of awareness of the benefits of maintaining machines, the lack of commitment to maintenance plans, the high cost of maintenance and poor user habits. Moreover, the market for machine spare parts is flooded with low quality parts which result in the repeated breakdown of machines. Creating a culture of maintenance of agricultural machinery is important because it is indispensable to obtain the benefits that come with the use of agricultural machinery.

4.10. Poor Status of the Local Agricultural Equipment Fabrication Industry

Majority of agricultural technologies fabricated in the Country cannot compete with a foreign counterpart. Hence, it deprives fabricators the opportunity for exportation which could earn them more income from foreign exchange and add to the nation's GDP.

4.11. Land Tenure System

By this law, all land belonging to the government; this has greatly hindered agricultural mechanization. Also, many formerly agricultural lands have been converted by the government to residential estates.

5.0. RECOMMENDATIONS and CONCLUSION

5.1. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made for the promotion and sustainability of agricultural mechanization in Nigeria:

1. A baseline survey on the status of agricultural machines should be done to provide current information on the level of mechanization in the nation.
2. The government of Nigeria should establish the long awaited agricultural mechanization policy with an efficient implementation strategy.
3. Importation should be controlled to strengthen local production of machinery and implements which can be manufactured locally.
4. Financial assistance should be made available to local fabricators and farmers at “no interest.”
5. The capacity of local fabricators should be improved through research and training home and abroad.
6. Prototypes and blueprints by government research institutions should be made available to local fabricators/ manufacturers for multiplication and commercialization.
7. The government should encourage public-private-partnership (PPP) investment in the agricultural sector to increase its capacity.

5.2. Conclusion

This work reveals that the level of agricultural mechanization in Nigeria is below FAO recommendation and can best be described as a low level of agricultural mechanization. The government is trying its best to improve it but more needs to be done with collaborations from the private sector and international organizations to make Nigeria self-sufficient in agricultural production. The absence of current information on the status of mechanization practices in the Country has hampered decision making, policy formulation, and implementation toward agricultural mechanization and food self-sufficiency. A survey of the current status of agricultural mechanization in Nigeria is seen as the first needed step towards the actualization of agricultural mechanisation and food sufficiency for over 180 million Nigerians populace.

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